

Correlates on the Knowledge and Management Practices on Pregnancy Induced Hypertension (PIH) Among Women in India

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Objectives: The study dealt into the level of knowledge and extent of management practices among pregnant diagnosed with pregnancy-induced hypertension (PIH) for the Calendar Year 2019. Additionally, the study determined which of the profile of the respondents influence the level of knowledge and extent of management practices on PIH. Lastly, it determined the relationship between the level of knowledge on PIH and the extent of management practices.

Methods: The study used the descriptive-correlational method of research. The 50 respondents diagnosed with PIH were selected on a total enumeration basis from the health institutions the researchers were able to visit from the period March- July 2019. The data are derived through the use of a questionnaire-checklist formulated by the researchers. Data are treated with the application of frequency and percentage, mean, multiple linear regression, and simple linear correlation analysis.

Results:

Findings of the study revealed that most of the respondents are 30-34 years old and 20-25 years old, are professionals, have a monthly family income of 20, 001 – 25, 000 pesos, got pregnant for the first time at the age of 20-23 and 16-19, are on their fifth pregnancy, have a history of hypertension during the past, are high school graduates, are married, are on their 1st to 13th week of pregnancy, and have no family history of PIH. The respondents have a "Fair" level of knowledge on PIH and have a "Very High" extent of management practices. The occupation of the respondents significantly influences the level of knowledge of PIH. Similarly, the presence of a family history of PIH affects the extent of management practices on PIH. Lastly, there is no significant relationship between the extent of management practices and the level of knowledge on PIH of the respondents.

Conclusions:

The respondents of the study have a moderate information on PIH which could be influenced by their nature of work. However, the way they manage their condition is found

to be very satisfactory which could be attributable to the familial predisposition. Nevertheless, the level of knowledge of the respondents on the risk factor of PIH had greatly influenced their health seeking behavior.

Keywords: pregnancy-induced hypertension, pregnant, knowledge, practices

INTRODUCTION

Pregnancy-induced hypertension (PIH) is one of the top causes of death among mothers during gestation and delivery. It is very frightening because it is clueless in terms of its symptoms until it will become severe. In addition to that, the exact cause is unknown; therefore, all pregnant women must practice precautionary measures for them to avoid its occurrence.

PIH also called gestational hypertension is manifested by high blood pressure during pregnancy. It can lead to a severe complication called pre-eclampsia, referred to as toxemia. Hypertension during pregnancy affects about 6- 8% of pregnant women. Women who are at risk of developing hypertension are: mothers for the first time, women whose sisters or mothers suffered from PIH, women having multiple pregnancy, women below age 20 and over 40 years old, and women who had blood pressure above normal range or kidney disorder before pregnancy (gestational hypertension also called pregnancy-induced hypertension.ph, 2015).

PIH complicates 6-10% of pregnancies. It is seen among women whose systolic blood pressure (SBP) is >140 mmHg and diastolic blood pressure (DBP) is > 90 mmHg. It is considered as mild if SBP is 140-149 and DBP is 90-99 mmHg, moderate if SBP is 150-159 and DBP is 100-109 mmHg, and severe if SBP is \geq 160 and DBP is \geq 110 mmHg. PIH refers to one of four conditions: a) pre-existing hypertension, b) gestational hypertension and preeclampsia (PE), c) pre-existing hypertension plus superimposed gestational hypertension with proteinuria, and d) unclassifiable hypertension. PIH is the main cause of maternal, fetal, and newborn illness and death. Womenfolk with PIH are predisposed to abruptio placentae, cerebrovascular events, organ failure, and disseminated intravascular coagulation (DIC). Fetuses of these mothers have more chance of having intrauterine growth retardation, prematurity, and intrauterine death (Kintiraki, Papakatsika, Kotronis, Goulis, and Kotsis, 2015).

According to Palacios and Pena-Rosas, as cited by Muti, Tsimanga, Notion, Bangure, and Chunzi (2015), globally, 10% of all pregnancies are complicated by hypertension, with pre-eclampsia and eclampsia being the chief reasons of maternal and prenatal morbidity and mortality. According to Arshad, Pasha, Khattak, and Kiyani as cited by Muti, Tsimanga, Notion, Bangure, and Chunzi (2015) it is also estimated that PIH affects about 5 – 8 % of all gravid women internationally.

Findings of the Philippine Health Statistics, as cited by Rachelis (2016), revealed that there is an increasing pattern of increase in the incidence of hypertension complicating pregnancy,

childbirth, and puerperium in the Philippines from 25.4% in 2000, 29.4% in 2005, 32.1 % in 2009, and 36.7 % in 2013.

In the Annual Operational Plan (AOP) of 2018 of the Provincial Health Office (PHO) of Ilocos Sur, Northern Philippines, hypertension is one of the causes of maternal mortality as of 2017. It accounts for 2 or 0.17% per 1,000 population.

In the province of Ilocos Sur, as reported by the Department of Health (DOH), Field Health Service Information System (FHSIS) (2012) as cited in Bermio (2015), maternal deaths were caused by hypertension.

The health workers, particularly nurses and midwives play a big role in the assessment of women who are at risk of developing hypertension during pregnancy. Educating women who are at risk is one of their primary responsibility. Moreover, it is also their responsibility to assist women, implement measures to alleviate the suffering of women suffering from pregnancy induced hypertension.

It is for this reason that the researchers conducted this study on the level of knowledge and management practices on PIH among women in Ilocos Sur. The study is in line with Sustainable Development Goal 3 in which the maternal mortality reduction remains a priority. "Goal 3: says: Ensure healthy lives and promote well-being for all at all ages" through 2030. The results would help the DOH formulate health strategies/programs to help women diagnosed with PIH. Also, the result would enable the nurses and midwives to formulate prompt, appropriate, and clinically sound intervention to help women manage and bring the pregnancy to success from conception to delivery and the postpartum period as well. For the academe, the College of Health Sciences and College of Nursing to integrate into its curriculum the discussion of hypertensive disorders during pregnancy. For the midwifery and nursing students, the result of the study would serve as a guide for them in providing health educations to high-risk women. For the respondents, the result of the study will create awareness on concepts of PIH. And lastly, for the researchers to plan what they can do to help pregnancy induced hypertensive women to cope with their present health situation.

The study focused on the level of knowledge and extent of management practices of pregnant women diagnosed with PIH at the selected hospitals and clinic and Municipal Health Offices (MHOs) in Ilocos Sur, Northern Philippines. Specifically, it sought to determine the socio-demographic, obstetrical, health-related profile, and hypertension status of the respondents. It also determined the factors that influence the level of knowledge and extent of management practices of the respondents on PIH. Lastly, it looked into the significant relationship between the management practices of the respondents and the level of knowledge of the respondents on PIH.

Theoretical Framework

Carson (2017) said that pre-eclampsia happens in 3-6% of all gestations, and the occurrence is 1.5 to 2 times higher in first time pregnancies. Additionally, hypertensive disorders in pregnancy may result to maternal and fetal morbidity, and they continue to be the most important cause of maternal mortality.

Sibai, Zhang, Zeisler, Hatch, Berkowitz as cited by Muti, Tsimanga, Notion, Bangure, and Chunzi (2015) claimed that PIH is a foremost pregnancy difficulty related to premature delivery, intra-uterine growth retardation (IUGR), abruptio placentae, and intra-uterine death, as well as maternal morbidity and mortality.

PIH strikes mostly the primigravida after the 20th to 24th week of gestation, and frequent occurrences are often seen at term. Patients are clueless about the symptoms of PIH; they also feel that they are not ill; they do not feel the changes unless the condition is becoming moderate to severe (Maputle, Khoza, and Lebesse, 2015).

James et al. as cited by Maputle, Khoza, and Lebesse (2015) discovered that multiparous women were aware of the condition, whereas primigravida did not know. This discovery was further supported by Calder and Dunlop as cited by Maputle, Khoza, and Lebesse (2015), wherein most of the pregnant women were aware of the potential risks of PIH because of their regular attendance at the antenatal clinic.

In a study conducted by Maputle, Khoza, Lebes (2015), the primigravida respondents are not fully aware of the signs and symptoms of PIH. They only knew a few signs and symptoms such as dizziness, swollen legs, headache, and sweating.

METHODOLOGY

The study used the descriptive correlational method of research. The 50 respondents diagnosed with PIH were selected on a total enumeration basis for the months of March, April, May, June, and July 2019 at the health institutions where the researchers were able to visit such as the Ilocos Sur Provincial Hospital- Gabriela Silang, Ilocos Sur Cooperative Medical Mission Group and Hospital, Metro Vigan Cooperative Hospital, Northside Doctors' Hospital, Reyes-Ulep Clinic and Hospital, Ilocos Sur District Hospital- Narvacan, and at the different Municipal Health Offices (MHOs) in Ilocos Sur such as Cabugao, Sto. Domingo, Caoayan, Santa, and Narvacan. Data are elicited with the use of a questionnaire-checklist formulated by the researchers and content validated by a pool of experts. Documentary analysis of the records filed at the hospitals and Municipal Health Offices (MHOs) was used to elicit obstetrical, health-related, and hypertension status of the respondents.

The respondents were requested to rate the items on a 5-point scale to describe the ratings based on their level of knowledge and extent of management practices on PIH. The researchers personally administered the questionnaire-checklist to the respondents. Before the administration of the questionnaire-checklist, approval was sought from the Chief of Hospital and the Municipal Health Officers. Data were treated and deduced through the use of frequency and percentage, mean, multiple linear regression analysis, and simple linear correlation analysis.

Below is the distribution of the respondents.

Table 1. Distribution of the Respondents

Hospital / MHO	Number of Respondents
Ilocos Sur Provincial Hospital- Gabriela Silang	29
Ilocos Sur Cooperative Medical Mission Group and Hospital	3
Metro Vigan Cooperative Hospital	2
Northside Doctors' Hospital	3
Reyes- Ulep Clinic and Hospital	3
Ilocos Sur District Hospital- Narvacan	3
Municipal Health Office- Narvacan	3
Municipal Health Office- Santa	1
Municipal Health Office- Caoayan	1
Municipal Health Office- Sto. Domingo	1
Municipal Health Office – Cabugao	1
Total	50

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table 2. Socio-demographic Profile of the Respondents

Personal Related Factors	<i>f</i>	%
Age		
35-39 years old	10	20
30-34 years old	11	22
26-29 years old	14	28
20-25 years old	11	22
19 years old and below	4	8
Total	50	100
Civil Status		
Single	18	36
Married	31	62
Separated	1	2
Total	50	100
Highest Educational Attainment		
Masteral graduate	2	4
Masteral Undergraduate	2	4
College graduate with MA Units	5	10
College Graduate	10	20

College Undergraduate	3	6
High School Graduate	24	48
High School Undergraduate	2	4
Elementary Graduate	1	2
Elementary Undergraduate	1	2
Total	50	100
Occupation		
Professional	19	38
Skilled	13	26
Unskilled	18	36
Total	50	100
Monthly Family Income		
25, 000 and above	8	16
20, 001 – 25, 000	15	30
15,001-20, 000	9	18
10,001-15, 000	4	8
5,001-10, 000	4	8
5, 000 and below	10	20
Total	50	100

On the Socio-demographic Profile of the Respondents

A great percentage 11 (22%) each of the respondents are 30-34 years old and 20-25 years old respectively, 15 (30%) have a monthly family income of 20, 001 – 25, 000 pesos, 19 (38%) are professionals, and 24 (48%) are high school graduates. The majority 31 (62%) are married.

Table 3. Obstetrical-related Factor of the Respondents

Age at First Pregnancy	<i>f</i>	%
40	1	2
32-35	2	4
28-31	7	14
24-27	12	24
20-23	14	28
16-19	14	28
Total	50	100
Gravidity		
5	4	8
4	14	28
3	10	20
2	18	36
1	4	8

Total	50	100.0
Age of Gestation		
28-41weeks	2	4
14-27weeks	7	14.0
1-13 weeks	41	82
Total	50	100.0

On the Obstetrical-related Factor of the Respondents

A great percentage 14 (28%) each of the respondents had their pregnancy for the first time at the age of 20-23 and 16-19, 18 (36%) are on their fifth pregnancy, a great majority, 41 (82%) are on their 1st to 13th week of gestation.

Table 4. Health-related Factors of the Respondents

Family History of PIH	f	%
with family history	14	28
without family history	36	72
Total	50	100
Family member w/ history of PIH	F	%
Aunt	1	7.14
Mother	10	71.43
Sister	3	21.43
Total	14	100.0
Presence of Co-morbid condition	F	%
Kidney Disorder	3	6.0
Diabetes Mellitus	6	12.0
Previous History of Hypertension	16	32.0
Heart Disease	3	6.0
Pregnancy Induced Hypertension Status	f	%
A. Eclampsia	2	4.0
B. Pre-eclampsia	47	94%
Mild	43	91.49
moderate	3	6.38
severe	1	2.13
Total	47	100
C. Chronic Hypertension	1	2.0
Grand Total	50	100.0

*Multiple Response

On the Health-related Factors of the Respondents

A great majority, 36 or 72% of the respondents have no family history of PIH. Among the 14 respondents with family history of PIH, it is their mother, 10 or 71.43 % who suffered from

PIH. A great percentage, 16 or 32 % of the respondents have history of hypertension during the past. Almost all, 47 or 94% of the respondents are diagnosed with pre-eclampsia.

Table 4. Level of Knowledge of the Respondents on PIH along Causes

Items	<i>f</i>	%
1.renal disease	10	20.0
2.stress	35	70.0
3.extra large uterus (multiple pregnancies, polyhydramnios, diabetes mellitus (DM))	21	42.0
4. history of high blood pressure before pregnancy	29	58.0
5. history of preeclampsia	24	48.0
6. history of diabetes mellitus (DM)	14	28.0
8. history of hydatidiform mole (H-mole)	14	28.0
8. obesity	25	50
9. nulliparity with extremes of age (below 20 and over 30-35)	18	36.0
10. low socio-economic status (low protein in the diet)	25	50.0
Mean Percentage		43.0
Descriptive Rating		Fair
Range	Item DR	Overall DR
81 – 100	Excellent (E)	Very High (VH)
61 – 80	Very Good (VG)	High (H)
41 – 60	Good (G)	Fair (F)
21 – 40	Poor (P)	Low (L)
1 – 20	Very Poor (VP)	Very Low (VL)

The respondents have a "Fair" level of knowledge on PIH along risk factor ($\bar{X} = 43.0$). The findings imply that the respondents are not fully aware of the causes and/or risk factors of PIH.

When taken singly, the respondents have a "Very Good" level of knowledge on "stress as a risk factor of PIH" (70.0), have a "Good" level of knowledge on item "history of high blood pressure prior to pregnancy as a risk factor to PIH" (58.0), and have a "Very Poor" knowledge on "renal disease as a risk factor to PIH".

The "Fair" level of knowledge of the respondents on PIH along causes specifies that the respondents are not completely aware of the possible explanations of why pregnant women suffer from PIH.

Table 5. Level of Knowledge of the Respondents on PIH along Signs and Symptoms

Items	<i>f</i>	%
1.high blood pressure in women who have not had high blood pressure before	30	60.0

2.high level of protein in their urine	24	48.0
3.rapid weight gain caused by a significant increase in bodily fluid	35	70.0
4.severe headaches	28	56.0
5.reduced urine or no urine output	24	48.0
6.dizziness	29	58.0
7.blurring of vision	24	48.0
8.excessive vomiting or nausea	27	54.0
9.epigastric pain	28	56.0
10.seizure	26	52.0
Mean Percentage		55.30
Descriptive Rating		Fair

The respondents have a "Fair" level of knowledge on PIH along signs and symptoms (\bar{X} =55.30). The findings imply that the respondents are not fully aware of the clinical manifestations of PIH.

As a whole, the respondents have "Very Good" level of knowledge on the item "rapid weight gain caused by a significant increase in bodily fluid" as a sign and symptom of PIH (70.0), have "Very Poor" level of knowledge on the item "dizziness" as a symptom of PIH (58.0), and have a "Good" level of knowledge on the items: "high level of protein in their urine", "reduced urine or no urine output", and "blurring of vision" as signs and symptoms of PIH.

Table 6. Level of Knowledge of the Respondents on PIH along Prevention

Items	<i>f</i>	%
1.consume less salt	36	72.0
2.drink at least 8 glasses of water a day	41	82.0
3.increase prenatal check-up	39	78.0
4.more protein in the diet	37	74.0
5.left side lying position to promote blood circulation.	33	66.0
6.adequate rest	38	76.0
7.avoid drinking alcohol	40	80.0
8.avoid beverages containing caffeine	39	78.0
9.do not eat junk foods	37	74.0
10.intake of calcium rich foods	33	66.0
Mean Percentage		74.6
Descriptive Rating		High

The respondents have a "High" level of knowledge on PIH along prevention (\bar{X} = 74.6). The findings imply that the respondents are aware of the necessary measures to avoid the occurrence of PIH.

The respondents have an "Excellent" level of knowledge on the item "drink at least eight glasses of water a day" (82.0) and a "Very Good" level of knowledge on the items "avoid drinking alcohol" (80.0) and "avoid beverages containing caffeine" (78.0).

Morikawab as cited by Townsend, O'Brien, and Kahlil (2016) stated that the incidence of preeclampsia could be reduced through increased water intake. They further said that increasing water intake is essential in maintaining a normal blood volume and placental blood circulation.

Table 7. Level of Knowledge of the Respondents on PIH along Treatment

Items	<i>f</i>	%
1. fetal movement monitoring every 2 hours and report for any changes to the physician	33	66.0
2. hospital admission for pre-eclampsia	33	66.0
3. magnesium through an IV to prevent seizures	27	54.0
4. antihypertensive drug (methyldopa) as prescribed.	22	44.0
5. diuretics to increase urine output	23	46.0
Mean Percentage		55.2
Descriptive Rating		Fair

The respondents have a "Fair" level of knowledge on PIH along treatment ($\bar{X} = 55.2$). The findings imply that the respondents are not fully aware of the different management of PIH.

The respondents have a "Very High" level of knowledge on the items "fetal movement monitoring every 2 hours and report for any changes to the physician" and "hospital admission for pre-eclampsia" (66.0) and have a "Good" level of knowledge on the item "magnesium through an IV to prevent seizures".

Townsend, O'Brien, and Kahlil (2016) stated that all women diagnosed with preeclampsia should be advised for confinement to hospital for ultrasound assessment of fetal growth since these women are at high risk of placental inefficiency. Women who will be diagnosed with severe preeclampsia or have significant signs and symptoms of impending eclampsia (severe headache, clonus, neurological impairment) should be given with magnesium sulfate for eclampsia prophylaxis. Magnesium sulfate is believed to cause a 50%–67% reduction in the risk of seizures and maternal death.

Table 8. Level of Knowledge of the Respondents on PIH along Complication

Items	<i>f</i>	%
1.fetal growth restriction because preeclampsia affects the arteries carrying blood to the placenta	30	60.0
2.preterm birth	23	46.0
3.placental abruptio	18	36.0
4.cardiovascular disease	23	46.0

5.HELLP Syndrome(Hemolysis, Elevated Liver Enzyme, Low Platelet Count)	27	54.0
6.stroke	38	76.0
Mean Percentage		53.0
Descriptive Rating		Fair

The respondents have a "Fair" level of knowledge on PIH along with complication (\bar{X} =53.0). The findings imply that the respondents are not fully aware of the difficulties of PIH.

The respondents have a "Very Good" level of knowledge on the item "stroke" as a complication of PIH (76.0) and "Good" level of knowledge on the item "Fetal growth restriction because preeclampsia affects the arteries carrying blood to the placenta", and have "Poor" level of knowledge on the item "placental abruptio" as a complication of PIH (46.0).

PIH brings about many fetal complications. Fetal complications include absence of blood supply to the uterus, placental abruption, intrauterine growth retardation, death in utero or premature delivery (Perkins, nd).

Table 9. Summary Table of the Level of Knowledge on PIH

Items	\bar{X}	DR
Causes	43.0	Fair
Signs and Symptoms	55.3	Fair
Prevention	74.6	High
Treatment	55.2	Fair
Complication	53.0	Fair
As a whole	56.22	Fair

As a whole, the respondents have a "Fair" level of knowledge on PIH (\bar{X} == 56.22). The result maybe because a great percentage of the respondents are just high school graduates and got pregnant at an early age at 16-19 years of age.

The respondents have a "Very Good" level of knowledge on prevention (\bar{X} = 74.6) and have a "Good" level of knowledge on treatment (\bar{X} = 55.2) and complication (\bar{X} =53.0).

The findings of the study oppose the conclusion of the research study of Ouasmani et al. (2018) wherein the familiarity of women residing in Morocco or the Netherlands regarding clinical manifestations related to hypertensive disorders of pregnancy was very restricted, if not absent.

The findings is similar to the result of the undertaking of Ouasmani (2018). Base on his qualitative inquiry, the majority of the respondents have inadequate knowledge on the indications of hypertensive disorders during the prenatal period both in Morocco and in the Netherlands. Half of the women did not know any symptoms at all and guessed some symptoms. Symptoms cited were a headache, edema, abdominal pain, dizziness, and

tiredness. No woman was able to enumerate at least three symptoms. One woman was assertive that sweating was the symptom of PIH.

Table 10. Extent of Management Practices on PIH along Nutrition

Items	Mean	DR
1. avoid eating fatty foods/ high in cholesterol	4.16	Often
2. avoid eating salty foods	3.86	Often
3. avoid starch	4.26	Always
4. eat a balanced diet	4.38	Always
5. eat fresh fruits	4.52	Always
6. eat vegetables	4.18	Often
Overall	4.23	Very High

Norm:

Range	Item DR	Overall DR
4.21 – 5.00	Always (A)	Very High (VH)
3.41 – 4.20	Often (O)	High (H)
2.61 – 3.40	Sometimes (So)	Average (A)
1.81 – 2.60	Seldom (Se)	Low (L)
1.00 – 1.80	Never(N)	Very Low (VL)

The respondents have a "Very High" extent of practices on PIH along nutrition with an overall mean rating of 4.23. The findings imply that the respondents adhere to a proper diet to maintain their well-being.

They "Always" eat fresh fruits ($\bar{X} = 4.52$), eat a balanced diet ($\bar{X} = 4.38$), and "Always" avoid starch ($\bar{X} = 4.26$).

Numerous educations have suggested the increased intake of fruits, vegetables, and vegetable oils, the regular drinking of folate and iron, the avoidance of fried foods, processed meat, and salty snacks, and the non- consumption of alcohol and beverages containing caffeine as means for the prevention of preeclampsia (Rasouli, Pourheidari, & Gardesh (2019).

Torjusen et al. as cited by Rasouli, Pourheidari, and Gardesh (2019), said that in Norway, it was found out that women who consume organic vegetables "often" or "most often" develop preeclampsia at a lower rate than women who prefer to eat non-organic vegetables.

Schoenaker et al. as cited by Rasouli, Pourheidari, and Gardesh (2019), recommended the consumption of fruits, vegetables, and folate during gravidity as ways of preventing the incidence of preeclampsia.

Lastly Merialdi as cited by Rasouli, Pourheidari, and Gardesh (2019) said that in a study conducted in the year 2003 reported that there is a 75% chance in the reduction of the incidence of preeclampsia with the consumption of antioxidants.

Table 11. Extent of Management Practices on PIH along Rest and Sleep

Items	Mean	DR
1. rest for two to four hours a day	3.86	Often
2. sleep 7-10 hours at night	3.94	Often
3. take a nap at least 30 minutes in the afternoon	3.88	Often
4. do walking for at least 15 to 30 minutes since it is the best form of exercise during pregnancy	4.33	Always
5. do forms of mental relaxation, like listening to music.	4.51	Always
Overall	4.10	High

The respondents have a "High" extent of practices on PIH along rest and sleep with an overall mean rating of 4.10. The result of the study means that the respondents perform ideal duration of rest and physical activity for a hypertensive pregnant.

The respondents "Always" do forms of mental relaxation, like listening to music ($\bar{X} = 4.51$), do walking for at least 15 to 30 minutes since it is the best form of exercise during pregnancy ($\bar{X} = 4.33$), and "Often" sleep 7-10 hours at night ($\bar{X} = 3.94$).

Rios, Bermio, and Bautista (2014) found out that most of their respondents diagnosed with PIH exercise once a day and the majority exercise for 30 minutes session.

Relaxing physical activities like stretching workouts, walking, using static bicycles; and modification of the inactive lifestyle are other processes recommended for the control and inhibition of the increasing rate of PIH (Rasouli, Pourheidari, & Gardesh, 2019).

Kasawara et al. as cited by Rasouli, Pourheidari, and Gardesh (2019) found that physical exercise has a protective effect against preeclampsia. They said that women who were at a higher risk of developing preeclampsia, stretching exercises may have a better protective effect against the condition.

Magnus as cited by Rasouli, Pourheidari, and Gardesh (2019), claimed that in their study in Norway (2008), women who had regular physical activity showed a 20% reduction in the incidence of preeclampsia.

Rudra et al. as cited by Rasouli, Pourheidari, and Gardesh (2019), claimed that pregnant who had a higher engagement in physical activity during the year prior to their pregnancy had 78% chance of developing preeclampsia compared to women who never performed exercise during this exact period.

Table 12. Extent of Management Practices on PIH along Health Seeking

Items	Mean	DR
1. take drugs as prescribed	4.48	Always
2. attend clinic on scheduled dates	4.04	Often
3. seek medical care when I feel something wrong even it is not my schedule	3.78	Often
4. when experience breathlessness		
a. just stay in bed	3.78	Often
b. assume semi sitting position	4.08	Often
c. assume left side lying position	4.31	Often
5. Take antihypertensive drugs as prescribed like methyldopa	4.51	Always
6. Manage edema by:		
a. elevating feet during the night	4.51	Always
b. sitting with legs elevated on stool.	4.43	Always
Overall	4.21	Very High

The respondents have a "Very High" extent of practices on PIH along health seeking ($\bar{X} = 4.21$). The outcome means that the respondents adhere to prescribed management and regularly attend to the clinic visit. Moreover, they are already strictly monitored by the health workers and that they are forced to comply with the health care assisted interventions.

The respondents "Always" take antihypertensive drugs as prescribed and manage edema by elevating feet during the night ($\bar{X} = 4.51$) and manage edema by sitting with legs elevated on a stool ($\bar{X} = 4.43$).

In a study conducted by De Vera and Uyheng (2018) on the knowledge and management practices on PIH among midwives, it found out that midwives administer antihypertensive medicines, where Methyldopa was most usually given. Among those who give Methyldopa, majority of them were had training on BEmONC.

Rasouli, Pourheidari, and Gardesh (2019) claimed that encouraging pregnant women at high risk for preeclampsia to adhere to their medical regimen and to make regular and more frequent doctors' visits is, therefore, highly recommended.

Townsend, O'Brien, and Kahlil, (2016), made mention that the standard and regularly used antihypertensive medications during the prenatal period are methyldopa and nifedipine. Methyldopa is the drug of high-quality for the Medicines and Healthcare Products Regulatory Agency (MHRA) because of an extensive history of use.

Table 13. Extent of Management Practices on Pregnancy Induced Hypertension along Substance Use

Items	Mean	DR
1. never smoke cigarette.	4.69	Always
2. avoid drinking alcohol.	4.73	Always
Overall	4.71	Very High

The respondents have a "Very High" extent of practices on PIH along substance use ($\bar{X} = 4.71$). The findings imply that the respondents adhere to healthy habit to maintain their well-being.

They "Always" avoid drinking alcohol ($\bar{X} = 4.73$) and never smoke a cigarette ($\bar{X} = 4.69$).

The findings conform to the study conducted by Rios, Bermio, and Bautista (2014), wherein the majority of their respondents diagnosed with PIH do not smoke. Most of the respondents do not drink alcoholic beverages.

Table 14. Summary Table on the Extent of Management Practices on PIH

Items	Mean	DR
Nutrition	4.23	Very High
Rest and Sleep	4.10	High
Health Seeking	4.21	Very High
Substance Use	4.71	Very High
As a whole	4.31	Very High

As a whole, the respondents have a "Very High" extent of management practices on PIH ($\bar{X} = 4.31$). They have a "Very High" extent of management practices on PIH along substance use ($\bar{X} = 4.71$), nutrition ($\bar{X} = 4.23$), health seeking ($\bar{X} = 4.21$), and "High" along rest and sleep ($\bar{X} = 4.10$). The findings maybe due to the fact that the respondents strictly comply to the health teachings of the health care providers such as the midwives and nurses who are the front line in the community health care system. Through the delivery of specific interventions by the health workers such as educational program and targeting of high-risk group, it could improve maternal practices and management of PIH.

Table 15. Results of the Multiple Regression Analysis of the Influence of Socio-Demographic, Obstetrical-related Factors, and Health-related Factors on the Level of Knowledge on PIH

Variables	Beta	t-value	t-prob
Socio-Demographic Factors			
Age	-.437	-.821	.428

marital status	-.011	-.033	.974
highest educational attainment	-.238	-.599	.560
Occupation	.655	2.421*	.032
monthly family income	-.032	-.089	.931
Obstetrical- related Factors			
age at first pregnancy	.513	1.085	.299
Gravidity	.168	.325	.751
Parity	-.220	-.569	.580
Gestation	.464	1.251	.235
Health-related Factors			
family history of PIH	.109	.427	.677
presence of co-morbid condition	.009	.029	.977
Mult. R: .734	F-ratio: 1.168		
R ² : .539	F-prob: .396		

Table 15 reveals that there is no significant effect of the combination of the socio-demographic, obstetrical-related factors, and health-related factors to the level of knowledge on PIH of the respondents. The finding is based on the computed F ratio of 1.168, which did not attain a significance at 0.05 probability level. The result of the study means that the level of knowledge on PIH of the respondents is not influenced significantly by the combination of socio-demographic, obstetrical-related factors, and health-related factors.

The table further shows that based on the value of R² (.539), 53.9 percent of the variance of the level of knowledge on PIH of the respondents is not attributed to the socio-demographic, obstetrical-related factors, and health-related factors of the respondents.

Taken singly, it was found out that the occupation (2.421) of the respondents significantly influences the level of knowledge on PIH. This implies that those professional respondents tend to have a higher level of knowledge on PIH. The result may be due to the knowledge gained from the workplace, accessibility to the different sources of information like the internet, newspapers and magazines and information from co-workers.

All the other factors like age, marital status, educational attainment, monthly family income, age at first pregnancy, parity, gestation, family history of PIH and presence of co morbid condition do not significantly influence the level of knowledge on PIH.

The result of the study conforms to the endings of the study of Mulud, Hamsah, Mohamad, and Nordin highlighted the association between socio-demographic characteristics such as age, educational levels, with knowledge of PIH among mothers in the pre-birth period. All the other socio-demographic factors like the age, marital status, highest educational attainment marital status, and monthly family income; and the obstetrical-related and health-related factors bear no significant effect to the level of knowledge on PIH.

The outcomes of the study oppose the findings of James et al. as cited by Maputle, Khoza, and Lebesse (2015) wherein multiparous women were aware of the condition whereas primigravida did not know.

The result of the study also contradicts the one conducted by Maputle, Khoza, Lebeso (2015), in which gravidity affects the level of knowledge on PIH. In their study, it was found out that the primigravida respondents are not fully aware of the signs and symptoms of PIH. They only knew few signs and symptoms such as dizziness, swollen legs, headache and sweating.

Also, the result of the study opposes the study conducted by Ouasmani et al. (2018), wherein the findings showed that women knew that hypertensive disorder in pregnancy is a related disease during pregnancy. The awareness of the respondents was due to the presence of a family history of PIH.

Table 15. Results of the Multiple Regression Analysis of the Influence of Socio-Demographic, Obstetrical-related Factors, and Health-related Factors on the Management Practices on PIH

Variables	Beta	t-value	t-prob
Socio-Demographic Factors			
Age	-.519	-1.193	.256
Marital status	-.210	-.772	.455
Educational attainment	.046	.141	.890
Occupation	-.218	-.988	.343
Monthly family income	-.001	-.004	.997
Obstetrical-related Factors			
Age at first pregnancy	.489	1.268	.229
Gravidity	.561	1.328	.209
Parity	.308	.974	.349
Gestation	-.386	-1.275	.227
Health-related Factors			
Family history of PIH	-.459	2.197*	.048
Presence of co-morbid condition	-.188	-.762	.461
Mult. R: .832		F-ratio: 2.255	
R ² : .693		F-prob: .087	

Table 15 reveals that there is no significant influence of the combination of the socio-demographic, obstetrical-related factors, and health-related factors to the extent of management practices on PIH of the respondents. This is based on the computed F ratio of 2.255, which did not attain a significance at 0.05 probability level. This means that the extent of management practices on PIH of the respondents is not influenced significantly by socio-demographic, obstetrical-related factors, and health-related factors.

The table further shows that based on the value of R² (.693) 69.3 percent of the variance of the extent of management practices on PIH of the respondents is not attributed to the socio-demographic, obstetrical-related factors, and health-related factors.

When taken singly, the presence of family history of PIH (2.197) is significantly related to the management practices on PIH of the respondents. This finding implies that respondents with family history of PIH tend to have higher extent of management practices on PIH. This

result means that respondents who have family members who had been diagnosed with PIH are more religious in the application of the different forms of management of PIH since they have learned the different forms of management from their family members.

Table 16. Correlation Coefficients on the Relationship between the Level of Knowledge on PIH and the Management Practices

Level of Knowledge on PIH	Management Practices on PIH				
	Nutrition	Rest and Sleep	Health Seeking	Substance Use	As a whole
Risk factor	-.222	-.154	.291*	-.281	-.248
Signs and symptoms	-.050	-.128	-.178	-.211	-.064
Prevention	-.167	-.189	-.112	-.152	-.203
Treatment	-.215	-.247	-.141	-.253	-.205
Complication	-.138	-.261	-.063	-.259	-.131
As a whole	-.220	-.256	-.241	-.321*	-.242

As a whole, there is no significant relationship between level of knowledge on PIH and the extent of management practices on the PIH of the respondents. This means that regardless of the level of knowledge of the respondents on PIH, their extent of management practices was more or less the same.

When taken singly, the level of knowledge along risk factor is significantly related to the extent of management practices on PIH of the respondents along health seeking (0.291). The result of the study implies that respondents who have a higher level of knowledge on the risk factor of PIH tend to have a higher extent of health seeking behavior. The outcome of the study means that the respondents who are more knowledgeable on the risk factor of PIH tend to seek more consultation from health professionals, religiously take prescribed drugs, and adhere more to the different interventions recommended by the health professionals.

The outcome of the study conforms to the findings of Cline et al., Schiffer et al., Bruggink et al., and Dickson, as cited by Pswarayi (2010) that the majority of women who have inadequate knowledge on PIH tend to have limited PIH self-care. The self-care aspect includes adherence to the recommended diet, taking of prescribed medications, having adequate rest. He further stated that poor symptoms management leads to poor self-care practices and hypertension control.

CONCLUSIONS

The respondents of the study have a moderate information on PIH which could be influenced by their nature of work. However, the way they manage their condition is found to be very satisfactory which could be attributable to the familial predisposition. Nevertheless, the level of knowledge of the respondents on the risk factor of PIH had greatly influenced their health seeking behavior.

RECOMMENDATIONS

The following are the recommendations forwarded by the researchers: (1) The Department of Health and the Academe must join efforts to enhance the level of knowledge of the respondents by conducting free and regular seminars, training programs, lecture, and symposium. These agencies must see to it that women must have better access to facts regarding pregnancy induced hypertension; (2) The health care professionals, especially those in the Municipal Health Office (MHO), should conduct information dissemination on pregnancy induced hypertension. Education materials such as flyers, posters, visual aids, and pamphlets must be provided; and (3) The academe must comprehensively discuss the topic of pregnancy induced hypertension.

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